
TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

In this article you may see the lack of English language teachers in primary schools makes teaching English to young learners a challenge. Because of this, primary school instructors are required to teach English in the second, third, and fourth grades even though they lack the necessary educational background and English proficiency. By taking into account elementary school teachers' and English language teachers' shortages. This study looks at the difficulties these primary school teachers had, how they were resolved, and how the course on teaching English to children affected the ideas of prospective teachers. In order to respond to the research questions and analyze the data, which were acquired through unstructured interviews, a cross-sectional qualitative research strategy was adopted in this study.

Key words: international language, language learning process, learning atmosphere, target language.

Globalization impact creates teaching English has developed dramatically in recent years and encouraging everyone to master English as their international language. English begins to be taught earlier to young learners as an evidence of development of English education in Indonesia. It is expected that English instruction at elementary level would contribute to the advancement of students' overall language competence. As expressed "learning a second language is a long and complex undertaking" that includes different variables such as learner, learning atmosphere, learning materials, environmental factors, and teachers. The difference between second language and foreign language learning also makes it

harder for the Turkish students to acquire a language successfully. In this acquisition process, teaching which is the process of “showing or helping someone to learn how to do something, giving instructions, guiding in the study of something, providing with knowledge, causing to know or understand” and teachers are two of the main characters. The successes of the teachers and the methods they use in the classroom have a significant effect on language learning process.

English is taught as a course in both middle and high school, as opposed to primary school, where there is no solid ground to teach English. This gap highlights the significance of developing a curriculum for young learners. The importance of this study lies in its attempt to enable young learners to acquire native-like proficiency in the target language, especially given the current need for English for economic growth in which English is a key term, scientific advancement in which technology is more governed by the target language, and culturally to communicate more effectively in foreign soils. This research was conducted in the form of a descriptive study. Descriptive research is used to describe a phenomenon and its features. The phenomenon described in this context is teaching strategies used by English teachers in teaching English to young learners. Observations and interviews were the primary data collection methods used in the study. This study's data is explained and analyzed in order to answer questions or solve problems. The observation sheet and interview guide were used as data collection methods and instruments. In this study, the researcher observed the strategies used by teachers in teaching English to young learners, as well as the frequency of each strategy used by teachers in teaching English to young learners. Young students In order to collect data, the researcher was present in the classroom sessions. The researcher used a camera and a notebook to document what happened during the English teaching process. In qualitative research, an interview guide is a conversation with a specific purpose to support the data. In order to gather information, the researcher interviewed the English teacher. The interview

was conducted to provide information about the strategies, the frequency of strategies, and the difficulties that teachers face when teaching English to young learners. The interview types used in this study were semistructured interviews. These strategies were used by the teacher with consideration toward four skills. In listening skill, the teacher tended to use listen & repeat and listen & do. Meanwhile, in speaking skill, teacher applied question and answer. On the other hand, for reading and writing skill, teacher tended to use guided written, in-pair, and cooperative learning. In listening skill, the teacher asked the students to do listen and repeat activity where the teacher said some words and the students followed exactly teacher's utterance. The teacher stood up and said the words while the students repeated it loudly in their seat. The teacher also told the meaning of those spoken words. After repeating, then the students were asked to do listen and do. In this strategy, the teacher spoke the words and the students followed what teacher said to his students. In this case, the teacher stood up in the front of the class to say the word. Then, the students who knew the meaning of words would act directly. This kind of activities make students have positive interaction with their environment because they can directly join the situation. Students get improvement on their vocabulary where they are encouraged to listen in their environment.

In conclusion, The strategies used by teacher were not able to involve children in the learning process. This was caused by teacher's lack of knowledge of teaching young learner. The teacher did not have educational background to teach English to young learners. However, every teacher should be creative in designing the learning process and this includes selecting the appropriate strategy. Teacher with lack of knowledge and experience of teaching young learners should be aware that the teaching and learning process should be fun and able to make young learner enjoy the learning process in an engaging way.

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